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FINANCIAL SECTOR DIGITALIZATION

Abstract. The article reveals the state program “Digital Kazakhstan” in the field of digitalization of the financial sector, according to which a wide range of measures are being implemented aimed at eliminating the barriers existing in the country for the development of Internet commerce in general, as well as increasing the competitiveness of local players. The development of financial technologies and non-cash payments is described. The issue of online cash registers and electronic invoices is touched upon. The concept of electronic government is revealed. The availability of public services in the online format became possible due to the provision of electronic digital signatures (EDS) to citizens on a free basis. A number of advantages of the portal of electronic public procurement were announced. In addition, the problems of digitalization of the financial sector are highlighted, among which the scale of computer crime in the banking and financial sector and in the field of violation of constitutional rights and freedoms of man and citizen, including privacy, personal and family secrets, plays an important role. The article also contains a list of necessary measures to ensure information security.

Keywords: digitalization, public services, procurement.

According to the message of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan “The third modernization of Kazakhstan: global competitiveness” dated January 31, 2017 and the decree of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated December 12, 2017 No. 827, the state program “Digital Kazakhstan” was approved, the purpose of which is to accelerate the development of the republic's economy and improve the quality of life population through the use of digital technologies in the medium term, as well as the creation of conditions for the transition of the economy of Kazakhstan to a fundamentally new development trajectory, ensuring the creation of the digital economy of the future in the long term. One of the tasks we are considering is the development of electronic commerce, financial technologies and non-cash payments.

The program involves the implementation of a wide range of measures aimed at eliminating the existing barriers in the country to the development of Internet commerce in general, as well as increasing the competitiveness of local players. The proposed measures lie in the field of regulation of electronic commerce, increasing the acceptance of electronic payments, increasing digital and financial literacy of the population and entrepreneurs, promoting electronic commerce, developing infrastructure and logistics, and so on.

As part of the regulation, issues are regulated to improve consumer protection in e-commerce, including effective remote tools for filing appeals to the relevant authorities, the possibility of

returning goods at the expense of the merchant, the introduction of a unified register of e-commerce market participants and others aimed at increasing the level of confidence of the population and participants, as well as to stimulate the transition of business to online trading.

The creation of a support infrastructure, including direct and indirect measures, including the creation of service support centers for e-commerce, is also becoming a priority.

Issues are being worked out to expand the list of self-produced goods (works, services) by types of activity corresponding to the goals of creating a special economic zone “Park of Innovative Technologies” aimed at accelerating the development and spread of electronic commerce.

Facilitating access to concessional finance and lowering or eliminating certain taxes for e-commerce players will also improve the competitiveness of entrepreneurs and stimulate online business.

As part of increasing the acceptance of electronic payments, issues are being worked out to stimulate the introduction of a simplified mechanism for making mobile payments, taking into account international experience, developing a system of incentives for entrepreneurs to make non-cash payments, and ensuring a complete transition to the use of electronic invoices.

Development of financial technologies and non-cash payments.

The vision of the digital financial industry in Kazakhstan by 2022 assumes the formation of a proactive financial community that plays a key role in an efficiently functioning financial industry with a developed infrastructure of the payment services market.

The financial sector is undergoing transformation with the use of technologies such as distributed ledgers, the proposal of new financial instruments, and the simplification and acceleration of procedures through integration with government information systems. Thus, the proactivity of the financial community implies the implementation of open technologies and, in general, active cooperation of banks, infrastructure companies and companies from the field of financial technologies with each other, with the support of the National Bank's regulator to reduce the level of fraud in the online environment, introduce new services and products, and improve customer experience. increasing the stability of the financial system. In order to achieve the goals for the development of a proactive financial sector, measures are being taken to develop and emerge innovative organizations focused on the development of customer-oriented products and services, building ecosystems in both financial and non-financial services.

To ensure the security, simplification and development of digital services, including government, social and commercial, a remote identification model is being developed, including one based on various biometric indicators, based on the principles of a risk-based approach. The model assumes the identification of customers using a database of state and commercial companies, as well as the receipt of services by government agencies, commercial companies and in the social sphere (education, healthcare, population census, and others).

The introduction of a digital identity mechanism will become the underlying infrastructure. This will help build a universal digital environment for interaction and communication between financial institutions, customers, government agencies and organizations. This will qualitatively increase the level and efficiency of the provision of financial, government and other services.

Conditions are created for the provision of online services by insurance organizations with the possibility of concluding insurance contracts in electronic form, electronic exchange of information between the policyholder (beneficiary) and the insurer upon the occurrence of an insured event, damage assessment, the need to change the terms of the contract (after-sales service), as well as storage of the electronic contract in a single database on insurance and round-the-clock access of the client to the insurance contract.

The introduction of mechanisms and standards for the electronic interaction of financial organizations, government agencies, citizens and entrepreneurs will allow by 2022 to build a “paperless”, open and highly competitive financial sector that ensures the security of transactions and reduces transaction costs.

The financial sector will provide tools for the development of e-commerce and implementation of initiatives to create an innovation ecosystem so that payments can be made quickly, easily and reliably, counterparties are verified, and access to financial instruments for business development and government support instruments can be obtained.

Together with the construction of an infrastructure for paperless invoicing, as well as other documents on contractual relations, the interbank settlement system is being modernized for real-time interbank transfers, which would reduce transaction costs for SMEs, increase the confidence of B2B market participants in cashless instruments. settlements, as well as develop direct settlements between persons (individuals and legal entities).

Particular attention is paid to the development and implementation of a set of measures to stimulate cashless circulation. Measures of financial and non-financial support are being implemented for representatives of SMEs, holding events together with the largest international payment systems, banks and other market participants to improve the financial literacy of the population [1].

The main tasks of digitalization of the financial sector are optimization of business projects, strengthening the fight against corruption, as well as improving the quality of services provided.

In order to reduce the “shadow” economy, the Ministry of Finance is actively working on the widespread introduction of online cash registers in trade, which are an instrument of state control over cash flow, completeness and timeliness of cash receipts by business entities. Currently, the requirement for the mandatory use of cash registers applies to cash settlements carried out in trade operations, performance of work, provision of services through cash and payment cards. The use of online cash registers excludes tax audits from taxpayers. The use of online cash registers is the final link in traceability system – import or production – wholesale – retail.

The introduction of electronic invoices is aimed at creating a transparent system of relationships, which is favorable for bona fide taxpayers and creates problems for unscrupulous taxpayers. The mastery of electronic exchange of invoices by taxpayers made it possible to switch to paperless document flow technology, to obtain confidentiality of document exchange using an electronic digital signature, and to ensure a quick search and the convenience of verifying documents (<https://clck.ru/U8MG9>).

Also, for example, with the electronic registration of a legal entity on the “electronic government” portal, this person can now immediately, remotely open a bank account, which greatly simplifies the process of starting a business in Kazakhstan.

In 2006, for the first time in Kazakhstan, eGov.kz, an “electronic government” portal, was introduced. The availability of public services in the online format became possible due to the provision of electronic digital signatures (EDS) to citizens on a free basis. EDS allows you to receive the necessary government services and certificates without leaving your home.

More than 6 million people are users of the eGov portal today. Through its infrastructure, 760 electronic services and services can be implemented (<https://egov.kz/cms/ru/digital-kazakhstan>).

Currently, the web portal of public procurement (goszakup.gov.kz) allows for public procurement in real time, provides the publication of information about the needs of customers for the supply of goods, works, services, their consolidation, procurement procedures, supplier identification, conclusion of electronic contracts and their execution. Creates a level playing field among suppliers. Provides quick access to the accumulated information. Significantly reduces paperwork. Increases transparency and openness of the public procurement process. Reduces the number of offenses in the process of public procurement. Reduces budgetary costs for the purchase of goods, works and services for public needs. Provides a unified procedure for the formation and placement of the state social order (https://egov.kz/cms/ru/articles/procurement_portal).

At the same time, digitalization of the financial sector raises a number of problems. The scale of computer crime in the banking and financial sphere and in the area of violation of constitutional human and civil rights and freedoms, including inviolability of private life, personal and family secrets, is growing significantly. In addition, private information is hacked (unauthorized penetration into it), the scale and number of coordinated computer attacks on financial and economic objects are growing. Such unlawful actions can be resisted only by the combined efforts of all countries, by creating a global security architecture, including the introduction of uniform methods and rules for combating cybercrime, developing partnerships, maintaining constant contacts and cooperation.

Digital technologies make national economies vulnerable both from hackers and from transnational corporations and states.

Recently, the activity of technical intelligence and special services of individual states in the field of information and psychological impact on the destabilization of the financial and economic situation in various regions of the world has been increasing, which violates the sovereignty and territorial integrity of other states.

Information security requires:

- take good care of domestic labor resources;
- create better living conditions for programmers in comparison with foreign ones;
- invite the best foreign minds to citizenship;
- to develop and implement effective competitive electronic technologies;
- staffing (training people on the use of digital technologies);
- organization of continuous scientific research, contributing to the creation of promising digital technologies;

- ensuring cryptographic (digital) sovereignty;
- creation of digital information infrastructure.

Information security involves:

- innovative development of the electronic industry and information technology;
- elimination of the dependence of the domestic economy on foreign information technologies

and information security means;

- creation, development and mass introduction of domestic developments;
- provision of services based on domestic developments;
- creating competitive advantages for domestic companies;
- development of a domestic progressive electronic component base and production of electronic components to meet the demand of the domestic market with access to the world market.

Ensuring information security in the field of science, technology and education needs:

- in financing the basic sciences;
- freedom of scientific creativity without censorship and other restrictions;
- development of scientific and technical potential in the field of information security;
- creation and implementation of effective and stable information technologies [2].

References

1. Decree of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated December 12. 2017. №827. On approval of the State Program "Digital Kazakhstan"
2. Петров А. А. Цифровизация экономики: проблемы, вызовы, риски // Торговая политика. 2018. №3(15), С. 9-31.

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